

Jill Santopolo's "The Light We Lost": Speech Act Analysis

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Abstract

The researcher examines the American novel "The Light We Lost" according to Searle's Speech Act theory in this paper. Many studies use speech act theory on political discourse, medical discourse, and even some literary works, but no one has studied Jill Santopolo's "The Light We Lost" according to Searle's speech act theory or any linguistics theory. Thus, the study tries to fill a gap in the survey by answering the following research question.

1. Is it possible to apply pragmatics theories to modern fiction?
2. What speech act features were introduced by Jill Santopolo's "*The Light We Lost*"?
3. What speech act is used more than others in the selected text "The Light We Lost"?

Keywords: Speech Act Theory, Pragmatics in Literature, Modern Fiction Analysis, Jill Santopolo and The Light We Lost.

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1. Speech Acts

The British language philosopher John L. Austin founded the idea of speech acts. His thoughts were delivered in 1955 at Harvard University, known as "the William James Lectures." Later, this observation was published in Austin's famous book "How to Do Things with Words."

Austin introduces the basic terms of Speech Acts (Justová, 2006, p.6). As Lyons states, "Austin's main purpose was to challenge the view that the only philosophically (and also linguistically) interesting function of language was that of making true or false statements." (Lyons, 1981, p.173) Austin shows that there are undoubtedly additional functions (Justová, 2006, p.6).

J.R. Searle was one of Austin's students at Harvard University. Later, he became one of America's outstanding language philosophers. He states that all linguistic communication, such as making promises, giving commands, making statements, or asking questions, is performing speech acts. Understanding speech acts depends on the context in which they are completed. To decode the whole utterance and its suitable meaning. The speech acts are used in standard routine exchanges, drama, and jokes (Justová, 2006, p.6).

The speech act theory is one of the most brutal attempts to explain how language works. Speech Acts theory extensively influences language philosophy, communication, and linguistics (Mabaquiao, 2018, p.1). Austin (in Tsui, 1994: 4) states that produced utterances act speech acts. Meanwhile, Yule (1996: 47) defines speech acts as "action which is performed via utterances." Birner (2013) also states the same idea, saying that "uttering something means doing something." Thus, people can act only by saying something. In speech acts, the speaker can convey physical action simply via phrases and words.

(Hidayat, 2016, p.2). Austin distinguishes three types of acts in speech: locutionary, illocutionary, and perlocutionary actions. Leech (1983: 199) defines them briefly as follows:

Locutionary act: performing an act of saying something.

Illocutionary act: committing an act in saying something.

Perlocutionary act: reserving an action by saying something.

This can be understood with a simple example:

-Would you close the door, please?

The locutionary act in this utterance is only a question of explicit content (Close the door.) The illocutionary act represents a request on the part of the speaker. Meanwhile, the perlocutionary action shows the speaker's desire that the listener should go and close the door. (Justová, 2006, p.11)

These individual essentials cannot be constantly separated that easily. Bach and Harnish state that they are closely related in a considerable measure (Bach & Harnish, 1979, p.3).

2. Classification of Speech Acts

Searle in Levinson (1983: 240) classified speech acts into five categories:

a. Representatives

Representatives are speech acts in which the utterance reflects the truth from the speaker's interpretation. Thus, the words are produced according to the speaker's observation of certain things. If the speaker says *she's beautiful*”, this fact or opinion is founded according to their observation. Statements of descriptions, facts, conclusions, and assertions are all examples of the speaker representing the world as s/he sees it. For instance, if someone states, *"The earth is flat,"* it means the speaker's view of the earth. Representatives' speech acts can be distinguished using some speech act verbs, such as inform, insist, remind, deny, correct, tell, assert, state, agree, claim, beliefs, guess, predict, report, describe, assure, and conclude.

b. Directives

Directives speech acts are when the speaker gets someone to do something. These speech acts include questioning, suggesting, requesting, orders, and commands. For instance, if someone says, *"Could you lend me a pencil, please?"*. In this utterance, the speaker requests the listener to lend him a pencil.

c. Commissives

In commissive speech acts, the speaker commits themselves to a future course of action, such as promising, pledging, threatening, refusing, or offering. *"I'll be back"* represents the speaker's promise that they will be back.

d. Expressives

Expressive speech acts express a psychological state, such as congratulating, thanking, welcoming, and apologizing. For instance, someone says, *"Don't be shy; my home is your home."* The utterance expresses receiving someone.

e. Declarations

In Declarations speech acts, the utterances create immediate changes in someone or institutional state of affairs, such as firing from employment, declaring war, marriage, christening, etc. For example, "*You are dead to me.*" (Hidayat, 2016, p.6)

3. Previous Study

In 2009, Al-Halawachy and Al-Bayati published a paper entitled "The Speech Act of Requestives in Iraqi Romantic Poetry with Reference." In which they study requests in a speech act. The proposal is any attempt for the speaker to ask the listener to do something. The researchers examine requestive speech acts in literary texts, especially Iraqi free verse poetry, which was revolutionary and created during the 20th century. They analyzed Al-Malaa'ikah's, Al-Sayyaab's and Blake's works. The study concludes that each poet uses requests to express their inner conflict feelings.

In 2011, Yarahmadi and Olfati examined "The Seagull," one of the well-known drama works by Anton Chekhov in 1896. The researchers use Speech Act Theory to explore the personalities of different characters in the play. The study was entitled "Speech Act Analysis of Anton Chekhov's The Seagull." The researchers establish a link between dramatic discourse and speech acts. According to Searle's speech acts, the study is commissive, expressive, assertive, directive, and declarative. The researchers conclude that speech acts theory helps reveal the hidden motives and intentions of characters in the play.

In (2015), Hashim studied Speech Acts in Political Speeches. The researcher selected the political speeches of John Kerry during his Presidential Campaign in 2004 and George Bush's Inaugural address in 2001 as both speeches have the same specific goals. The study examined only Twenty sentences from the two selected lectures. The findings show that Kerry depends more on cooperative acts as he makes a lot of promises. On the other hand, Bush used assertive acts more than other speech acts.

Chen and Zhang (2019) study "Speech Act Theory and Its Application in the Titles of Articles in WeChat." The researchers selected the British philosopher John Austin's speech acts theory to study the daily language on the Internet. Among social media, they examine the titles of articles in WeChat. The study concludes good tags arouse the readers' curiosity. Additionally,

increasing the number of reader titles should be about some hot issues or people's daily lives. The labels need to be brief with some attractive words to emphasize something.

Ramanathan, Paramasivam, and Hoon (2020) write a paper entitled "Discursive Strategies and Speech Acts in Political Discourse of Najib and Modi," which examines the political discourse of Twitter of two Asian premiers: Former Prime Minister of Malaysia, Najib Tun Razak and Prime Minister Narendra Modi. The researchers used Searle's speech acts theory to examine prime ministers' tweets during election campaigns. This study explored the illocutionary actions of commissives and directives and Wodak's discursive strategies. Finally, the study concludes that the citizens are willing to obey and accept commands given by leaders for a better future.

In 2019, Fatimah Al-Mashhadani wrote a thesis entitled "Speech Acts in Doctor-Patient Linguistic Communication." In this study, she examines doctor-patient interviews according to the speech acts theory by Austin (1962). The study investigates seven medical interviews recorded at two internal medicine departments in Al-Batool Teaching Hospital and Baqubah Teaching Hospital / Iraq. The study aims to examine the frequencies of speech acts. The study concludes that the most repeated speech acts are questions and statements relevant to medical discourse. The doctor usually asks questions to make the best diagnosis.

Another study about medical discourse is represented by Susanthi el (2019) entitled "Speech Act Taking Place in the Medical Conversation." This study examines the five features of speech act and the maxim theory. The textbook "English for Midwives: Practical Guidance for Antenatal Care" is used as data. The study aims to analyze the speaker's intended meaning. The text is also rich with quantity and quality maxims.

Lastly, as mentioned above, many studies about speech acts; some use literature discourse, and others use political discourse in addition to medical addresses.

4. Methodology

The researcher selected Jill Santopolo's "The Light We Lost" (2018) and analyzed it according to Searle's Speech Acts Theory (SAT). The researcher selects four chapters from this novel as data. The chapters are from the beginning, middle, and ending to ensure they cover as much of the novel as possible.

5. Analysis of "The Light We Lost"

5.1 First Text

1. It's the most incredible view of New York City you'll ever see.
2. The whole sky was turning gray, the city shrouded in ash.
3. The tears filled my eyes.
4. There were people in those buildings.
5. We stood there, staring at the aftermath of destruction.
6. Tears dripping down both our cheeks...
7. Our eyes, still wet with tears

The first text is chapter three of the novel. The heroine Lucy meets the hero Gabriel Samson (for short, Gabe) during Shakespeare's class at Columbia University, precisely on 11 September 2001. The day that a plane hits the Twin Towers. In chapter three, the author describes how Lucy and Gabe go to the dorm's roof to see what is happening. "It's the most incredible view of New York City" from the top. This description is representative speech acts. However, because of the attack on the Twin Towers, the sky was grey, and New York City was covered with ash, as seen in (2), which is again a representative speech act. Lucy's eyes filled with tears at the sight, realizing people were "in those buildings." Lucy holds Gabe's hands while they stare at "the aftermath of destruction." Jill Santopolo depicted this scene in a very emotional way: "Tears filled my eyes," "Tears dripping down both our cheeks," and "Our eyes, still wet with tears," which is an expressive speech act as seen in (3, 6, and 7) in addition to using description to enrich the depiction of the scene as in (4 and 5) which is a representative speech act.

8. As if the only way to stay safe was to keep my lips on yours
9. I felt safe
10. I forgot the world. At that moment, there was only you.
11. I felt guilty about it...Guilty that we kiss.... guilty that I was able to lose myself in
you
12. Said I love you for the first time.
13. There's something about death that makes people want to live.
14. I we don't think you should blame us for it.
15. I listened to your heart and was comforted by its steady beating.

Even though they have just met and are strangers, Lucy and Gabe find comfort in each other. They kiss each other like "the only way to stay safe was to keep my lips on yours." This makes them feel safe. They forgot the world around them. This deep emotion in (8,9 and 10) is a representative speech act. Later, Lucy felt guilty for having their kiss on 11 September with the shadow of death around the city. Later, she knew many people got engaged and said, "Love you" for the first time that day. This is because the human desire to live increases around death. Thus, Lucy decides that she will not blame herself anymore. After that kiss, Lucy puts her head on Gabe's heart and feels "comforted." In all the above extracts, there is an expression for different kinds of emotion such as feeling "safe," "forgot the world," "I love you," "want to live," "blame," and "comforted." All these emotions are expressive speech acts.

Figure (1) *Use of Speech Acts in Chapter Three of "The Light We Lost"*

5.2 Second Text

1. I never told you how broken I was.
2. How I looked at the spaces your books left on the bookshelves.
3. I couldn't eat waffles without crying.
4. I burned my lips when I drank it,
5. And it dulled the pain.

6. I felt like hell the next morning
7. Learning how to live with the pain.
8. Because all I felt was your absence

The second text is XXII (22) in the novel. Lucy and Gabe now broke up after a wild relationship for fourteen months. In this chapter, Lucy is alone in the apartment, struggling with her sorrow. Everything around her reminds her of Gabe, the space his books left in the bookshelves after he gathered his stuff, "the spaces your books left on the bookshelves." She cannot eat waffles because they remind her of him. She can not cross many stores and restaurants because she has many memories there. She starts drinking all night, and in the morning, she feels "like hell"; thus, she does not go to her job. All the above extracts clearly express the feeling of pain and sorrow. Therefore, it is an expressive speech act such as: "pain," "broken," "crying," "felt like hell," and "your absence."

9. "I can't stay here."
10. I could not take it anymore.
11. How I was falling apart
12. I wrote with false cheer
13. I waited and waited and waited
14. I kept thinking about you
15. How you said you'd always love me
16. I'd feel a combination of rage and sadness, disappointment deeper than anything.

Staying in their apartment by herself reminds Lucy about their good times together. After staying there in depression for a couple of days, she decides she "can't stay here" and "could not take it anymore." Thus, she decides to move on with her friend Kate. She even sends Gabe an email with "false cheer," pretending she is doing good. However, Gabe does not reply. Lucy "waited and waited and waited" for an answer while she "kept thinking" about him, how Gabe told her they would keep in touch and that he always loved her. This waiting turns into "rage and sadness, disappointment deeper than anything." Again, all the above extracts are pure expressions of feeling; accordingly, they are expressive speech acts.

Figure (2) *Use of Speech Acts in Chapter Twenty-one of "The Light We Lost"*

5.3 Third Text

1. THERE WERE TWO TYPES OF PEOPLE IN THE WORLD- who loved giving gifts and others who loved receiving them.
2. Loved getting gifts and still do.
3. Loved giving gifts as well.
4. We were supposed to go with Darren's family
5. like to spend so much time with them
6. I'd miss my own family
7. His family promised a big Christmas tree
8. my brother had offered to watch her

In chapter XI (40), Lucy meets a nice guy named Darren during the summer. Now, it is Christmas, and they are planning it together. Lucy opens the chapter by stating that some people love giving gifts while others love receiving them. This is a representative speech act. Lucy loved getting presents for so long, but now, with Darren, she finds out she also loves giving gifts. She also likes spending time with his family, even though she misses her own family. This expression of a positive feeling of "loved," "like," and "miss" in extracts (2,3,4, and 6) are expressive speech acts. While any future commitment and promise is a commissive speech act as in "supposed to go with Darren's family," "my brother had offered to watch her," and "His family promised a big Christmas tree" in extract (4, 7, and 8)

9. My plan to spend Christmas with Darren's family
10. I don't want to love anymore
11. My feelings had clearly changed
12. I am happy for you, even if I'll miss you at Christmas
13. I'll miss you,
14. I'll see you when I get back
15. He was so excited about this holiday trip

Darren and Lucy plan to spend Christmas with Darren's family in Colorado. This planning for future commitment is a commissive speech act as in (9). Lucy calls her brother, Jay. Together, they recall when Lucy told him she "didn't want to live anymore" after her harsh break-up with Gabe. After a year and a half, she is in love again, and her feelings change, which is an expressive speech act. Jay uses an explicit speech act to express his happiness for his sister and that he would miss her at Christmas. She tells him that she is going to miss him as well. And they should meet when she comes back from Colorado. Again, this future commitment is a commissive speech act, as in (14). Darren is so excited about their Christmas together. This excitement is an expressive speech act.

16. He declared us all set to leave
17. The plan was for both of us to stay at the apartment
18. His eyes filled with tears.
19. The first time I'd ever seen him cry.
20. I felt like I was giving him some of the happiness that he'd showed me
21. Saw tears in his eyes
22. I love you so much that I don't know how my heart can stand it.
23. Show him how much I love him
24. The more I loved him

After double-checking their bags, Darren declares that they are ready to travel. This Declaration speech act. They plan to stay at Darren's apartment and head to the airport. This planning is definitely a commissive speech act. However, Darren has a terrible flu, and his eyes fill with tears when he tells Lucy he can not get out of bed. This is the first time Lucy sees him

crying. Thus, she decides to bring Christmas to him by decorating his house with a tree and putting all the gifts under it. To give him some "of the happiness that he'd given" her. When Darren wakes up and sees the Christmas decorations, he cries again, but this time out of happiness. He tells her he loves her so much, and she says the same. Here, the expression of the feeling of love in (22,23 and 24), Darren's tears and crying in (18, 19, and 21), and Lucy's attempts to make him happy in (20) is an expressive speech act.

Figure (3) Use of Speech Acts in Chapter Forty of "The Light We Lost"

5.4 Fourth Text

1. Mr. Samson is a brain-dead
2. Don't think about it,
3. Focus on what you're doing now
4. Stay strong
5. Think about his apartment
6. I missed them already
7. I wish I could hold them, feel their little bodies warm against mine.
8. I felt like an intruder.

The last text is the final chapter of the novel. Lucy married Darren, now has two kids, Violet and Liam, and is pregnant with her third child. She is still in touch with Gabe and even loves

him. Now Gabe is in intensive care after getting hurt in a bomb in Gaza. They call Lucy because she is listed as his emergency contact. Almost against Darren's agreement, Lucy flies to Jerusalem. Gabe suffers from extreme brain injury, and he is "a brain-dead." This is a representative speech act. After seeing him in intensive care, Lucy has a really harsh nervous breakdown. The doctor orders her a taxi to take her to Gabe's apartment. Lucy demands herself to "Don't think about it," "Focus on what you're doing now," and "Think about his apartment." These commands in (2,3, 4, and 5) are directive speech acts. Lucy is already missing her children. She wants to hold them to feel the warmth of their little bodies against her. This expression missing in extracts (6 and 7) is expressive speech acts. Moreover, entering Gabe's house, Lucy feels like "an intruder." This is also an explicit speech act.

9. There were boxes of books opened but not unpacked
10. A few photographs are framed and leaning against walls but not hung
11. rugs pattered in bold colors... A brown couch
12. A wooden desk piled with electronics and wires.
13. That's the farthest you'll ever read in that book.
14. I'll finish the book...I'll read it for you, Gabe.

His apartment still needs to be set up. It seems that he works like crazy. The boxes of books are open but need to be arranged. A few photographs are framed on the walls. There is a rug with bold colors and a brown couch. A desk filled with wires and electronics. These descriptions in (9, 10, 11, and 12) are representative speech acts. There is a book that Gabe's read till page 254. This is the "farthest you'll ever read in that book." He will never be able to finish it because his life is cut short. This is a representative speech act (a fact). Thus, Lucy promises to finish reading that book for him. This future is a commitment commissives speech act.

Figure (4) Use of Speech Acts in the fourth text of "The Light We Lost"

5. Conclusion

This paper studies the novel "The Light We Lost" by the American novelist Jill Santopolo. The researcher uses Searle's speech act theory. According to the research question, all the speech act classifications have been used in the selected texts. However, It is evident from the above analysis that the expressive speech act has been used more than any other type. The majority of the chapter in the novel describes the deep emotion of love, pain, break and loss. As shown in the table below.

Representatives	11
Commissive	8
Declarations	1
Expressives	47
Directives	4

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